

SOME VIEWS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES IN FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: The current article is devoted to formation of linguistic competence of future English teachers. Linguistic competence has sometimes been used as an idealized notion which somehow embodies the collective knowledge of a speech community in the person of an ideal speaker-hearer. However, the basic notion is the competence of an individual in a language. If the language in question is not the native language, it is taken for granted that the person may be proficient in the language to some degree. The standard is then generally set by native competence. However, native competence is itself a matter of degree. Consequently, objective criteria are required by which one may assess the competence of a person in one or more languages by a common standard. This presupposes a notion of linguistic competence which has empirical import. This work is dedicated to improving the system of forming the linguistic competence of future English teachers.

Keywords: reforms, standard, linguistic competence, modernization, civilization, competence, communicative competencies, CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference), integration.

After gaining independence, Uzbekistan was recognized by the developed countries and the international community for its socio-economic, political and spiritual development. The country's import and export potential has grown sharply, the use of modern equipment and technologies in industry, manufacturing, agriculture and other sectors has reached a high level, the results of gradual reforms have been recognized worldwide as the "Uzbek model" of education. The process of modernization of the system of continuing education in the country is being supported by the state. In particular, a legal framework aimed at protecting the legal interests of educational entities has been created, an integrated mechanism for training globally competitive personnel has been created, the content of education has been improved, the system of training and attestation of highly qualified scientific and scientific teachers has been adjusted to world standards. In the framework of the implementation of all reforms in the system of continuing education on the basis of the Law "On Education" and the "National Training Program" created a complex system of teaching foreign languages. This is because the constitution stipulates that the languages,

customs and traditions of all nations and peoples living in Uzbekistan must be respected and conditions must be created for their development. Indeed, 2012 marked a turning point in the training of highly qualified personnel in Uzbekistan who are fluent in foreign languages, have effective use of the achievements of world civilization and world information resources, and have a high communicative competence in international cooperation. These resolutions are aimed at increasing the effectiveness of foreign language learning: the teaching of foreign languages outside the 2013/2014 academic year begins in the first grade of general secondary schools; Separate teaching of sciences, technical and international products abroad languages, knowledge of foreign languages at each stage of education thematic criteria for assessing the level of concentration and the National Testing System development, new state education standards, curricula and plans, creation of textbooks, modern information in foreign language classrooms equipping with technical means of communication and teaching Accelerated program development, English language training and art publication of literature, television, newspapers and electronic magazines, introduction of distance education, Republican Scientific and Practical Center methodological support of English language teachers through the organization, Intensification of important work to ensure the quality of professional. development is carried out with. Thus, the modernization of teaching foreign languages, including English, in Uzbekistan is expected to lead to a number of positive results, a comprehensive system of training highly creative, highly competent teachers has been created on the basis of public demand. A mechanism of social partnership has been established for all categories of children to be modern thinkers, able to freely communicate with people of different nationalities, to use the achievements of world science in the development of society, to train competitive teachers in the global labor market. Special attention is now being paid to improving the quality of education, provided that the level of knowledge of future English teachers meets the level of C1. During the years of independence, special attention was paid to improving the quality of education in accordance with modern requirements, including the organization of the system of training foreign language teachers in accordance with international qualification requirements. As a result of comprehensive reforms in the field of education, in particular, a national system of training future foreign language teachers based on best international practices has been created. At the same time, there is a need to accelerate approaches to the formation of communicative competencies in improving the quality of training of foreign language teachers. The Action Strategy for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 sets tasks such as "educating a highly educated and intellectually developed generation, creating a pool of competent scientific and pedagogical staff in higher education institutions." is important. At a time of rapid integration and socialization in the social, economic and spiritual spheres in the world,

special attention is paid to research on the content and training of competitive teaching staff in accordance with international qualifications, the use of innovative educational technologies. In this regard, the activation of social communication in future English teachers, increasing sociolinguistic training, defining the professional profile of an English teacher is of great scientific and practical importance. Research on improving the competence of future foreign language teachers in the world is carried out in the following priority areas: Improving the pedagogical mechanism of training competent foreign language teachers in accordance with the requirements of international European CEFR standards; development of innovative technologies for developing the competence of future foreign language teachers; designing the process of organizing independent learning in the classroom and outside the classroom. Although research has been conducted by scholars in various fields on the problem of competency formation of future foreign language teachers, the issue of improving the system of competence formation of future English language teachers in accordance with international educational standards has not been studied. Leading research centers and higher education institutions around the world, including the United States, Canada, British Columbia, the People's Republic of China, the Russian Federation, pay special attention to the role of linguistic competence in human communication practice and activities, communicative approaches to language testing and innovative pedagogical technologies. On the basis of world research, scientific research is being conducted on technologies for the formation and development of linguistic competencies, the improvement of the methodological framework for the systematic organization of professional orientation of language education. It is also important to increase the effectiveness of models for the formation of communicative competence, the organization of interactive education on the basis of media technologies, the development of computer linguistics, the widespread application of language portfolio technology in education. It is an important element to discuss the linguistic competence related to teachers competence in the teaching and learning process because teachers have to design, implement develop the syllabus. In order to plan for the professional development of English language teachers, we need to have a comprehensive understanding of what competence and expertise in language teaching consists of. These are: language proficiency, content knowledge, teaching skills, contextual knowledge, language teacher identity, learner-focused teaching, specialized cognitive skills, theorizing from practice, joining a community of practice, and professionalism. Each construct will be examined, its contribution to teacher competence and performance illustrated, and implications discussed for the development of English language teachers and teacher education programmes. They are grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence and strategic competence. Language is absolutely central to your learning: without it, you cannot

make sense or communicate your understanding of a subject. You will need to develop your language skills, and specifically, your academic English, in order to: understand and make the most effective use of your study materials. Communicative language teaching involves developing language proficiency through interactions embedded in meaningful contexts. This approach to teaching provides authentic opportunities for learning that go beyond repetition and memorization of grammatical patterns in isolation. Communicative competence is a term in linguistics which refers to a language user's grammatical knowledge of syntax, morphology, phonology and the like, as well as social knowledge about how and when to use utterances appropriately. Linguistic competence is the system of linguistic knowledge possessed by native speakers of a language. It is distinguished from linguistic performance, which is the way a language system is used in communication. In the generativist tradition competence is the only level of language that is studied, because this level gives insights into the Universal Grammar, that generativists see as underlying all human language systems. Functional theories of grammar tend to dismiss the sharp distinction between competence and performance, and particularly the primacy given to the study of competence. This is unaffected by "grammatically irrelevant conditions" such as speech errors. Therefore, increasing competitiveness in English teachers is one of the most important factors. Noam Chomsky introduced this concept in his elaboration of generative grammar, where it has been widely adopted and competence is the only level of language that is studied. According to Chomsky, competence is the ideal language system that enables speakers to produce and understand an infinite number of sentences in their language, and to distinguish grammatical sentences from ungrammatical sentences. This is unaffected by "grammatically irrelevant conditions" such as speech errors. In Chomsky's view, competence can be studied independently of language use, which falls under "performance", for example through introspection and grammaticality judgments by native speakers. Many other linguists and others – have rejected this distinction, critiquing it as a concept that considers empirical work irrelevant, leaving out many important aspects of language use. Linguistic Competence by Noam Chomsky is somewhat similar to Saussure's concept of language and parole. Competence, by Chomsky, refers to the native speaker's knowledge of his language, the system of rules, his ability to produce and understand. Performance on the other hands is the study of the system of rules; performance is the study of actual sentences themselves, of the actual use of the language in real-life situation. So the speaker's knowledge of the structure of language is his linguistic competence and the way in which it is uses his linguistic performance. Refined as before, competence is an underlying mental system underlying actual behavior, linguistic institution ability to analyze language, ignoring mistakes, understanding new sentences, even producing new sentences. In short, competence is a set of principles which a speaker masters,

performance is what a speaker does. As competence is a kind of code, performance is an act of encoding or decoding. Competence concerns the kind of structures the person has succeeded in mastering and internalizing, whether or not he utilizes them, in practice, without interference from the many of the factors that play a role in actual behavior. For anyone concerned with intellectual processes, or any question that goes beyond mere date arranging, it is the question of competence that is fundamental. Obviously one can find out about competence only by studying performance. In this way the abstract, internal grammar which enables a speaker to utter and understand an infinite number of potential utterances is a speaker's competence. Linguistic competences are related to the use of language through the expression and interpretation of concepts, thoughts, feelings, facts, and opinions in order to perform oral and written discussions. Such interactions may take place in diverse social and cultural contexts, which will determine the characteristics of the language written or spoken, such as the grammar, pragmatic, and sociolinguistic characteristics. Linguistic competences are highly related to communication competences and they are even seen as equal. Within scientific production and communication, linguistic competences are related to the adequate use of language, especially written, and they are characterized by: the adequate use of written language and structuring of content; reading and writing of scientific documents in the reader's native language; and reading, writing, and translation of documents to other nonnative languages, particularly in the most used, translation may not indicate a complete proficiency of another language, but it must be good enough to allow its reading and interpretation. Linguistic competences are also related to information competences, because the correct writing of scientific documents and the description of research findings demand the demonstration of information seeking, selection, compilation, and processing competences, which are supported in the comprehension and production of scientific texts for diverse audiences. Linguistic competences involve a set of skills, knowledge, and attitudes that are interrelated and mutually supported in order to conduct a successful scientific communication that may be destined to different communities or audiences, who will be able to understand the communicated knowledge and even use it, provided that they have been correctly materialized from a linguistic point of view. Linguistic competence, communicative competence, and interactional competence have had a profound impact on second language teaching, learning, and testing. Although a substantial number of studies have been conducted on these three competencies, they have not been conflated for discussion in a single study. It is an important element to discuss the linguistic competence related to teachers' competence in the teaching and learning process because teachers have to design, implement, and develop the syllabus. Language is what enables people to articulate things, ideas and attitudes in an intelligible form and to transmit the results to other people. More recently, linguists have recognized the

importance of language in identities. Language enables us to express who we think we are and how we are connected with other people. You can not make any achievement in the study of language if you do not take 'competence' into consideration. In conclusion, the four language skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing are important in order to improve everyday life communicative interactions. The level of professional competence of future English teachers is their ability to understand and interpret linguistic signals, correct pronunciation, memorize new words at certain moments, communicate freely in a dialogic, monologue manner, prepare presentations, skills of expression, fluency of speech, requirements of the society to teachers, scientific-theoretical knowledge of the norms of professional competence, level of understanding of the essence, translation skills, ability to implement information about the socioeconomic and cultural life of the country where the language is studied evaluated with. In the process of globalization, it is important to train teachers who meet world educational standards, think modern, competitive, innovative pedagogical technology and information and communication technologies, as well as fluent in several foreign languages. In the training of quality foreign language teachers in line with modern requirements, it is important to determine the measures within the government, the creation and implementation of the legal framework. Indeed, in this regard, it is expedient to ensure the quality and effectiveness of the professional competence of future foreign language teachers, including English, the didactic features of the formation of scientific-theoretical, methodological, practical competence. In the formation of professional competence of future English teachers leads to effective results in the identification and effective use of competence criteria, pedagogical principles, typology of competencies, competency indicators, innovative forms of education, methods, tools, didactic factors.

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